

Personal Hygiene of School-Going Children in Nagpur City, Maharashtra, Central India.

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Abstract Aim-

This study was performed to assess the personal hygiene and assess cleanliness habits of school-going children in Nagpur city, Central India. Along with nutritional status also collected information regarding the personal hygiene of students. Sample Size – The sample size that was used in the study was 264 respondents (School going children 13-15yrs). Sampling technique- Structured questionnaires were prepared to collect information from the respondents. Purposive sampling techniques were followed to gather information for this study. Maximum respondents 61.5% replied that they brushed their teeth once in a day and minimum respondents replied that they brushed their teeth twice in a day.

A maximum number of respondents 99.2% said that they were taking baths twice a day and 0.8% said that they were not taking baths twice a day. Introduction Personal hygiene is a self-care practice that people carry out to maintain their health. These practices are fundamental to the prevention of many diseases, especially contagious diseases. Personal hygiene includes hand, and face hygiene, regular bathing, hair care, and washing and using own clothes, towels, shoes, and slippers

Introduction

Health and hygiene are closely related and essential for maintaining a healthy lifestyle. Good hygiene practices include regular hand washing, bathing, brushing teeth, and grooming. These actions help prevent the spread of germs and disease and promote overall cleanliness and well-being. Eating a balanced diet, getting regular exercise, and getting enough sleep are also essential aspects of maintaining good health. Practicing good hygiene and healthy habits can help prevent illnesses and improve overall health and well-being. It's important to note that good hygiene should be taught to children from a very young age, as this will help them form healthy habits that will last them a lifetime (Gauri Malik 2023)

Objectives

1. To know the personal hygiene of school-going children.
2. To know the habits of cleanliness of school-going children.

Methodology.

Sample Size – The sample size that was used in the study was 264 respondents (School going children 13-15yrs).

Sampling technique- Structured questionnaires were prepared to collect information from the respondents. Purposive sampling techniques were followed to gather information for this study.

Kumar *et al.*, (2022) said that personal hygiene refers to a set of individual practices and conditions that help maintain health and prevent the spread of diseases. Maintaining personal hygiene is important for social health, physical health, and psychosocial

health. The present study aimed to assess the knowledge and reported practices of school-going children regarding personal hygiene to develop an information booklet. The study adopted a cross-sectional design to collect data from 410 school-going children in rural villages of Haldwani block, Uttarakhand. The children were recruited via a convenient sampling technique. It was found that the majority (n=230, 56.09%) school going children had moderate knowledge of personal hygiene. The overall practices of children were found to be appropriate for 366 (89.51%) children. Regarding knowledge and hygienic practices, a mother's education plays a vital role in school-going children. Also, teachers with parents can play a pivotal role in providing health education regarding personal hygiene from an early stage of childhood itself for longevity and to protect from illnesses.

Punjab. International Journal of Nursing Research. The study's objectives were to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and relationship between rural and urban school-aged children's knowledge and attitudes about personal hygiene. Methods: The study used a comparative research design. A stratified random sample selection procedure was utilized. One hundred samples (50 from rural areas and 50 from cities) were selected. The population of the study was rural and urban school-going children 9–11 years. To examine the data, descriptive and inferential statistics were employed. Results: The survey concluded that 40% (20) of rural schoolchildren and 44% (22) of urban schoolchildren had strong knowledge. About 96%

(48) urban and 88% (44) rural schoolchildren valued personal cleanliness. The mean knowledge score of urban schoolchildren was 19.48, higher than rural children's 16.52, and their mean attitude score was 74.18, much higher than rural children's 68.10. The mean knowledge score of rural and urban children was statistically significant for age, mother's education, and source of information, but not for household type or monthly income. In rural children, class was significant while gender was non-significant. The mean attitude score of rural and urban school children was statistically significant for age, gender, and class, but not for mother education, type of family, family monthly income, or source of information. Based on the study.

Singh, S., Das, N., & Sahoo, P. (2019) said that for kids, maintenance of personal hygiene helps to enhance the standard of life and longevity. Hygiene springs from "Hygeia" the divinity of health in Greek mythology. Hygiene is one every of the most important a part of life. one in every of the foremost effective ways in which we've to safeguard ourselves from sickness is nice personal hygiene. Personal hygiene facilitates to prevention/reduce kid mortality from communicable diseases, injuries, and different health issues by implementing the academic program, and health education. An interventional study was taken to find out the level of knowledge relating to personal hygiene, measure the effectiveness of role-play on knowledge relating to personal hygiene among school-going kids, and verify the association between the pre-test knowledge score with selected socio-demographic variables. The abstract framework adopted for the study supported the modified Widen back clinical nursing theory (1964). In this study purposive sampling techniques were accustomed choose a hundred school-going children (10-12 years) who are meeting the sampling criteria.

Singh, Niti Talsania (2015) The present study was conducted among 1378 school-going and 697 non-school-going children of 10 to 18 years of age during the period December 2012-December 2014. Result: The majority 24.86% of non-school-going urban children have poor personal hygiene followed by 20.79% of non-school-going urban children. Poor personal hygiene was seen in just 9.77% of School going children in urban areas and 13.43% in rural areas. The statistical difference in poor personal hygiene among school-going and non-school-going children of the urban area was highly significant. Conclusion: There were huge differences in overall occurrence of personal hygiene, it was found to almost double among non-school children compared to school children. Non-school children were the most vulnerable group."

Brij Pal Singh & Mahak Sharma found that good nutrition means a stronger immune system, low illness, better health, and productive society. In India, most school-age children are malnourished, mainly undernourished. This review has been done to know the prevalence of wasting, stunting, overweight, and obesity among children in rural as well as urban areas of different areas in India. For this purpose, thirty studies were reviewed by using different sources such as Research Gate, PubMed, Google Scholar, American Journal of Clinical Nutrition, and surveys of different agencies such as websites of the Ministry of Women and Child Development Government of India and different state governments. Dietary recalls structured interviews and anthropometric measurements were used in all the studies for data collection. Results from various studies show that underweight children range from 6.6% to 83%. Prevalence of stunting ranges from 13.8% to 56.1%, prevalence of wasting ranges from 6.7% to 75%, and prevalence of underweight ranges from 6.6% to 83%. It was concluded that malnutrition is a major problem in children and a lot of attention is needed to combat the problem.

Khatoon, Sachin B2, Khan, and Srivastava(2017) found personal hygiene plays a major role to promote a healthy life. This study was performed to assess the current level of knowledge and practicing behaviour regarding hand washing, bathing, tooth brushing, and taking care of nails and hair. A cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted on 800 students of the Lucknow district. All the students were interviewed with a structured questionnaire (pretest). A visual display of good and bad personal hygiene was shown on the projector and explained the benefits of good personal hygiene behaviour. Again, a structured questionnaire was given (post-test). Most of the students belonged to the 10-12 years age group. The knowledge of the students regarding general body cleanliness was 87.5% in the post-test as compared to 53.8% in the pretest. Keeping the hair well-trimmed was considered a part of personal hygiene by 38.0% of students

Rekha Shekhawat (2019) stated that good personal hygiene since childhood is not maintained, it will lead to various contagious diseases like gastroenteritis, skin infections, etc. So present study was done to assess knowledge and practice regarding personal hygiene in school-going children. Methodology: This cross-sectional study was conducted on 1008 students of 6th to 12th class from government schools of Bikaner. A semi-structured Performa was used. Result: More than 90% of students knew body, clothes, and teeth hygiene, 46% about the use of toilet paper, and 29.8% about sanitary pads. More than 90% bath, brush teeth every day, hand wash before a meal and

after using the toilet. Less than 70% hand wash after handling an animal, or cutting nails. A major source of knowledge for students was schools (71%). Conclusion: Good knowledge and practice were found regarding certain points but still more awareness and promotion are necessary for better personal hygiene in students.

Result and Discussion

1. From the above study it was found that N=120 (45.5%) respondents were male and N=144 (54.5%) respondents were female.
2. In the age category 104 (39.4%) respondents belongs to the age group of 13 and 14 years respectively while N=112 (21.2%) belongs to the category of 15 years of age.
3. 3.37(28%) respondents reported a height of 4 feet to 5 feet, 134(50.8%) were found to be in the category of 5 feet to 5.5". N=23(17.4%) reported their height of 5.6" to 6 feet and 3.8% were fall under the category of 6 feet.
4. In the weight category 42.2% of respondents reported their weight below 40kg and 42.4% reported under the category of 41-50kg. 9.8% of respondents belong to the category of 51-60kg and 4.5% of respondents fall under the category of 61-70kg.
5. Maximum respondents 61.5% replied that they brushed their teeth once in a day and minimum respondents replied that they brushed their teeth twice in a day.
6. Of the Maximum number of respondents 99.2% said that they were taking baths twice a day and 0.8% said that they were not taking baths twice a day.
7. 17.1% said that they cited their nails once a week as well as 22.9% cited their nails twice a week.
8. Of the Maximum number of respondents 88.5% said that they changed socks daily and only 11.5% said that they were not changing socks daily.
9. From the observed data maximum of 93.1% of respondents said that while washing their hands they used soap and water while a few 6.9% said that they used only water for washing their hands.
10. When asked about washing hands before meals maximum of 96.9% of respondents gave a positive response and only 3.1% replied negatively for the same.
11. Maximum respondents 99.2% said that they washed their hands after use of toilets to maintain their hygiene and only 0.8% said that they didn't wash their hands after use of toilets to maintain their hygiene.
12. Of a Maximum number of respondents 87% said that they washed their hands after sneezing

and only 13% said that they didn't wash their hands after sneezing.

13. From the observed data maximum of 79.4% of respondents said that they used hand sanitizer whenever required and 20.6% of respondents said that they were not using hand sanitizer whenever required.
14. Maximum respondents 96.2% said that they washed their hands after touching the pets/animals and 3.8 % said that they didn't wash their hands after touching the pets/animals.

Summary and Conclusion

This study was performed to assess personal hygiene and to know the cleanliness habits of school-going children in Nagpur City, Central India. From this study, it was found that N=120 (45.5%) respondents were male and N=144 (54.5%) respondents were female. Maximum respondents 61.5% replied that they brushed their teeth once in a day and minimum respondents replied that they brushed their teeth twice in a day. The Maximum number of respondents 99.2% said that they were taking baths twice a day and 0.8% said that they were not taking baths twice a day.

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